

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type1_b_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:05:58 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	17.51	µm	
Size:	65531	digits	
Spacing:	0.2672	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type1_b_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:05:58 AM		
Studiabale type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	5.177	μm	
Min:	-2.862	μm	
Max:	2.316	μm	
Size:	193798	digits	
Spacing:	0.02672	nm	
NM-points ratio:	4.606 % (414556 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:05:58 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	5.177	μm	
Size:	193798	digits	
Spacing:	0.02672	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.5932	μm	
Ssk	-0.6044		
Sku	4.723		
Sp	2.312	μm	
Sv	2.865	μm	
Sz	5.177	μm	
Sa	0.4537	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.7404	%	
Smc	0.6712	μm	
Sxp	1.408	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	18.05	μm	
Str	0.2456		
Std	33.75	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1598		
Sdr	1.220	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.02403	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vv	0.6952	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmp	0.02403	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmc	0.5054	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvc	0.6096	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvv	0.08563	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	2.748	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.5863	µm
Mean density of furrows	3819	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	180.0	°
Second direction	33.76	°
Third direction	89.97	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	71.34	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

